

Analytical strategies combining multi-elemental isotopic dilution with external calibration for rapid and precise inorganic wine profiling by ICP-QQQ-MS: high geographic discrimination for improved wine management and traceability

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ABSTRACT

Quality assessment in wine often relates to certainty of geographical origin. A large array of multi-elemental approaches has been developed in this sense. This paper presents a new method based on combined multi-elemental isotopic dilution (MID) and external calibration for the determination of 23 elements (characteristic of the soils, agricultural practices and anthropogenic contaminations) by ICP-QQQ-MS. First, the ICP-MS operating parameters were optimized. Then, the improvements brought by MID compared to external calibration were evaluated. The method, combined to six different multivariate statistical treatments, was finally used to analyze samples originating from the three hills of the DOC Jurançon from the South-West region of France covering a very small geographical area of about only 1000 ha. Depending on the statistics applied, the discrimination between the hills could be achieved with a mean accuracy of 100%.

1. Introduction

In the last 20 years, the interest of consumers in the quality and provenance of food identified has steadily increased (Gilg & Battershill, 1998). This is particularly true for wine which can be considered to be routinely implemented in the daily diet. It can also be considered a luxury product and, in this case, can be highly subjected to false origin and fraud. This aspect concerns both daily wines with DOC (Denomination of Controlled Origin) or PDO (Protected Designation of Origin) but also more prestigious “Châteaux”. Many stakeholders in this field are interested in the development of methods allowing the reliable wine assessment in terms of geographical origin authentication.

Various analytical approaches have been proposed for wine

authentication. The first one is based on the establishment of the organic compounds profile by NMR (¹H, ²H, and ¹³C) (Le Mao et al., 2023) or mass spectrometry (Schartner et al., 2023). They allow the determination of several dozens of organic constituents and compounds, which leads to good classification rates. For example, Godelmann et al. (2013) managed to discriminate German wines with an accuracy rate on average of 89% and Gougeon et al. (2019) discriminated Bordeaux wines from other French wines with an overall correct classification of about 95%. However, the instability of some markers like phenolic compounds may produce variations over time and make challenging the comparison of the same sample over time (Mac et al., 2023). Another approach is based on the stable isotope measurements by IRMS, particularly ¹⁸O in wine water that is positively correlated to the relative

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humidity a few weeks before harvesting (Hermann & Voerkelius, 2008). It was notably used to discriminate wines from Central and Eastern Europe and Argentina (Horacek et al., 2021). However, as weather conditions play a fundamental role in this isotopic pattern, the year of harvest is crucial and past vintages cannot be used to evaluate current vintages (Christoph et al., 2003). In the last decade, the introduction of MC-ICP-MS has allowed the democratization of the measurement of the isotopic ratios of non-traditional elements (Sr, Pb, B). This approach relatively new is very powerful for tracing the wine origin. For example, the determination of the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio (together with total Sr) has been shown to be efficient to discriminate Bordeaux wines (Epova et al., 2019) and a three isotopic ratios system ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$, $^{208}\text{Pb}/^{207}\text{Pb}$ and $\delta^{11}\text{B}$) was proved to discriminate sparkling wines (Champaign, Cava and Prosecco) (Cellier, 2020). However, the high equipment price, the time-consuming and costly sample preparation becomes a limitation of this technique, particularly if a comprehensive database is to be constructed.

To overcome these limitations (stability over time, dependence on weather conditions or cost of the analysis), the elemental profile by ICP-MS and/or ICP-AES is becoming the most common approach used for the wine authentication. It has been used for example to discriminate wines from Argentina (Azcarate et al., 2015), France (Hao et al., 2021), California (da Costa et al., 2020), Romania (Feher et al., 2019), Italy (Rapa et al., 2023), Portugal (Rocha et al., 2019), Spain (Astray et al., 2021; Perez-Alvarez et al., 2019), Germany (Castineira et al., 2004), Croatia (Leder et al., 2015), Russia (Temerdashev et al., 2024), North-Eastern coast of the Black Sea (Oganesyants et al., 2024), China (Gao et al., 2022; Su et al., 2024), South Africa (Coetzee et al., 2005) or Greece (Pasvanka et al., 2021). However, all these studies focus on individual countries, or even regions, which limits the broader applicability of the findings. To our knowledge, the only study that covered worldwide samples (more than 12,000 samples from 17 countries) was from Sarlo et al. (2024). The authors reached mean accuracies of 92% for country classification. However, only half of the elements investigated were precisely measured and the results of the other half were interpolated between elements present in the calibration standard, applying response factors. This most probably leads to less precise and accurate results. One can assume that improving these two parameters could also improve the accuracy of the classification.

To date, quantification by isotopic dilution (ID) is one of the benchmark methods to improve precision and accuracy of an analysis (Fassett & Paulsen, 1989). ID is based on the addition of known amounts of an isotopically enriched substance to the analyzed sample. This spike contains the analyte in a different isotopic composition. After complete mixing of the sample and spike, the resulting isotopic ratio reflects the analyte concentration in the sample. ID is therefore able to automatically correct matrix effects, instrument instability and signal drift, resulting in higher accuracy and precision of the results. Moreover, compared to the standard addition method, which requires several calibration points, ID is one-point calibration, making it interesting for routine analysis (Heumann, 2012). Another significant advantage also lies in the fact that this method is the closest to trace back to the IS systems. This is most important when setting up a very large database since all the data generated will be directly traceable to the IS with excellent precision. ID has already been applied for multi-element determination in water (Raposo et al., 2014), in lead fire (Compernelle et al., 2012) or in pharmaceuticals (Korbi et al., 2025). Despite the fact that the technique of choice to perform the elemental profile in wine is ICP-MS, consistent with a quantification by ID, to our knowledge, ID has never been used to evaluate it.

Further, considering the huge number of variables generated, multivariate analysis is essential to extract the relevant information. The chemometric tools available have been reviewed (Drivelos & Georgiou, 2012). They involve analysis of variance (ANOVA), principal component analysis (PCA), cluster analysis (CA), linear discriminant analysis (LDA), canonical discriminant analysis (CDA), regularized discriminant analysis (RDA), classification and regression trees (CARTs), soft independent

modeling of class analogy (SIMCA), k nearest neighbor (kNN), partial least square (PLS), and artificial neural networks (ANN). Rapa et al. (2023) compared seven of them to classify seven Venetian PDO wine samples and observed that the accurate classification rate of a PDO could significantly change from one tool to another (up to a factor of 2.5). Nonetheless, LDA, that calculates linear combinations of the original variables to maximize the separation between the different categories and minimize the variance within each category, has been mainly applied (Drivelos & Georgiou, 2012).

The aim of this study was therefore, in a first stage, to develop and evaluate the potential of multi-isotopic dilution (MID) using ICP-MS as detector to determine with very high precision the concentrations of elements in wine. In a second stage, the method developed has been applied to the discrimination of wines on a very small geographical scale, down to almost the km^2 scale, paying particular attention to the choice of multivariate statistic to be applied.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Samples

Different series of wine samples have been selected to address the potential of the analytical strategies. All samples collected were carefully controlled to ensure that they had a certified origin.

At first, a set of 25 samples of red and white wines was collected with very different provenances (7 from Spain, 11 from Italy and 7 from Tunisia) and was investigated both by external calibration and MID. These samples were selected since they covered wide differences in terms of soils and climate and displayed a wide variation in elemental content. They were used to optimize the MID method, evaluate its robustness, and finally allow comparing the performances of MID with respect to external calibration for multi-element determinations. Further, a unique sample resulting from an equal mixture of each of these 25 samples was prepared to address the validation of the method developed since, currently, no certified reference material for these 23 elements in wine exists.

In a second stage, in order to evaluate the full potential of the method using combined MID and external calibration, a larger set of samples coming from a small geographical area was used. The objective here was to evaluate the geographical potential of discrimination at the micro scale that we assume is the most difficult to achieve since soils variability at this scale is much less. The geographical area selected for this study was Jurançon ($n = 50$), an appellation in the South-West region of France. It covers a geographical area of about 1000 ha and is made of three different hills (Jurançon, Lasseube and Monein). Samples were provided by the winemakers themselves in order to have a full representativity of the small geographical area. They covered two different vintages (2021 and 2022), included both dry and sweet wines as well as organic and conventional wines. With the exception of two samples stored in a stoneware container, half of them had been stored in a wooden barrel and the other half in stainless steel tanks.

In order to evaluate the inter-bottle reproducibility, two different bottles of the same wine were analyzed and the results compared. This test was conducted for several wines covering different geographical origins.

2.2. Reagents, standards and solutions, elements selection for MID

Nitric acid (69–70%) and hydrogen peroxide (30%) were purchased from Fisher Scientific Bioblock (Illkirch, France). Ultrapure water (18 $\text{M}\Omega/\text{cm}$) was obtained from a Milli-Q system (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA).

For MID quantification, a custom-made spike solution containing 35 ng/g of ^6Li , 29837 ng/g of ^{10}B , 199 ng/g of ^{53}Cr , 14979 ng/g of ^{57}Fe , 120 ng/g of ^{61}Ni , 397 ng/g of ^{65}Cu , 7475 ng/g of ^{67}Zn , 1986 ng/g of ^{87}Rb , 2501 ng/g of ^{86}Sr , 71 ng/g of ^{95}Mo , 1 ng/g of ^{111}Cd , 504 ng/g of

^{137}Ba and 100 ng/g of ^{207}Pb was purchased from ISC (Gijón, Spain). The justification of these concentrations is discussed in the 3.1.2. section.

For the elements that cannot be measured by MID (mono-isotopic and major elements: Al, As, Co, Mn, V, Na, S, Ca, Mg, K), external calibration quantification was applied. For this, a mono-elemental stock solution containing $1000\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$ ($10,000\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$ in the case of K) were purchased from CPAchem (Trappes, France). All working standard solutions were prepared daily in ultrapure water.

2.3. Instrumentation

For sample digestion, a DigiPrep system (SCP Sciences, Courtaboeuf, France) was used.

Total element determination was carried out using a triple quadrupole ICP-MS (iCAP-TQe, Thermo, Bremen, Germany). The ICP-QQQ-MS measurement conditions were optimized daily to give the highest intensity using a standard built-in software procedure. The flexibility of the ICP-QQQ-MS has allowed for the application of different mass filter to address major elements as well as trace elements and to remove interferences on key major elements.

2.4. Analytical procedures

The detailed analytical procedure for the wine analysis is displayed Fig. 1. This figure highlights the dual calibration procedures combined (MID and external calibration) and their respective position in the full analytical flow chart. 13 elements were quantified by MID, namely Li, B, Cr, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, Sr, Rb, Mo, Cd, Ba and Pb. The concentrations of the mono-isotopic elements (Na, Al, Mn, Co and As) and of the major elements (K, Ca, Mg and S) were measured by external calibration.

2.4.1. Mineralization

A sample volume of 1 mL of wine was weighed in a 50 mL polypropylene tube (DigiTube, Courtagne Analyses Service, Mont Saint-Aignan, France) and then spiked by $100\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of the spike solution. The exact mass of the spike was noted. The combined mixture (sample + MID spike) was then digested with 1 mL of HNO_3 and $500\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of H_2O_2 using a heating block during 2 h at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The tube was then completed to 50 mL with ultrapure water. The solution was then analyzed by ICP-QQQ-MS. A wide array of sample preparations are available for wine, going from simple dilution to microwave digestion prior to detection (Pyrzynska, 2004). We have chosen to use a direct mineralization with hotblock since it allows the removal of the alcohol that may negatively impact the detection by ICP-MS and allows the simultaneous mineralization of several dozen of samples.

2.4.2. ICP-QQQ-MS operating parameters

The ICP-QQQ-MS operating conditions applied for each element are given in Supplementary Material. The objective of the mass filter tuning was to be able to measure the elements all at once, avoiding dilution, as the final goal is to build an extensive database at a reasonable price/sample throughput. The abundance of the elements investigated covers about 6 orders of magnitude (from the low $\mu\text{g/L}$ range for Cd to almost the g/L level for K). The measurement of the major elements would require a further dilution than the one applied for trace elements to protect the detector of the ICP-QQQ-MS. To avoid this step, the sensitivity of the ICP-QQQ-MS was artificially decreased for the measurement of the major elements. For this, dwell time was significantly decreased (by a factor 10) and the quadrupoles were used in the high-resolution mode to reduce the bandwidth and therefore the number of ions sent to the detector.

2.4.3. Calculations for quantification by ID

The analyte concentrations in the wine samples were calculated according to the following equation:

$$C = C_t \times \left(\frac{m_t}{m_s}\right) \times \left(\frac{M}{M_t}\right) \times \left(\frac{R_m \times A_{bt} - A_{at}}{A_a - R_m \times A_b}\right)$$

where C is the concentration of the analyte in the sample, C_t the concentration of the tracer, m_t the mass of the tracer added to the sample, m_s the mass of the sample uptake, M the natural atomic weight of the analyte, M_t the atomic weight of the analyte in the tracer, R_m the isotope ratio measured in the isotope-diluted sample, A_{bt} the abundance of the isotope b in the tracer, A_{at} the abundance of the isotope a in the tracer, A_a the natural abundance of the isotope a and A_b the natural abundance of the isotope b (with a being the most abundant isotope in the tracer and b the most abundant natural isotope of the analyte). The level of the spike of the tracer was considered valid if R_m was comprised between square root of (A_{at}/A_{bt}) and square root of (A_a/A_b) . In order to correct the mass bias effect, the isotope-diluted samples were bracketed by a sample of natural isotopic composition.

2.4.4. Statistical analysis

Data processing was performed using different statistical routines using the software JMP 18 (SAS Institute, Cary, NC, United States) combining statistical analysis capabilities with graphical visualizations.

Fig. 1. Analytical flow chart for the multi-elemental inorganic signatures using dual calibration methods, multi-isotopic dilution and external calibration, and their respective position in the analytical flow chart.

One-way ANOVA was used to evaluate the discriminating power of each element. Exploratory analysis by Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA), k Nearest Neighbors (kNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Naïve Bayes (NB) or Random Forest (RF) were also used to identify underlying patterns and address the probability of geographical origin assessment.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Choice of the analytical strategy

3.1.1. Relevance and selection of the elements to be measured

Inorganic elements play a major role in the development of the plant. The vine's mineral requirements depend on several factors: the type of soil and its fertilization (availability of mineral elements), the soil cultivation, grazing, irrigation, the root system and the availability of water (Carbonneau & Torregrosa, 2020). These conditions are key for promoting the fluxes of inorganic elements to the grapes. In terms of plant nutrition requirements, some elements are considered to be essential nutrients. They can also be considered as nutrients beneficial to the plant or, finally, as non-essential minerals. Essential elements could be Ca, Mg, Mn, Fe, ... These elements are most often in elevated concentration in the final product. Some beneficial inorganic elements, such as Co or Na, could be present in a concentration range in general lower than the previous elements. There is also an array of non-essential elements that are not implemented in the development of the plant but that are up-taken anyway. These elements can be Rb, Sr, Ba. Their concentration is also very different and they are good markers of the geogenic signature of the soils.

Further from the direct uptake from the soil, the man-made addition of fertilizers or pest products such as copper sulfate (Bouillie Bordelaise) may add another inorganic signature to the wine content. Then, atmospheric inputs are also to be considered when looking at elements such as Pb (Cellier, 2020; Epova et al., 2020). Finally, the production process with eventual storage conditions may add slight additional inorganic signatures.

The wide variety of elements involved means that, in terms of analytical requirements, the method developed must take into account both major and trace elements, as they all provide complementary information. However, measuring almost all the elements of the periodic table would be too costly for a questionable benefit. Indeed, a literature review has shown that all the elements did not have an equivalent discrimination power. Elements such as Ca, Sr, Rb, B, Li, Na, Ba, etc. were among the most regularly cited as reliable for assessing the authenticity of wines, regardless of their origin (Cellier et al., 2022). For a first approach, a set of 23 elements has therefore been selected: Li, B, Na, Mg, Al, S, K, Ca, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Rb, Sr, Mo, Cd, Ba and Pb. They represent a mixture of major and trace elements, markers of soil composition (Sr, Rb, ...), agricultural practices (Cr, V, ...) or anthropogenic contamination such as Pb, for example (Cellier, 2020; Cellier et al., 2021).

3.1.2. Selection of the quantification method

One reason why the evaluation of isotopic ratios of non-traditional elements (Sr, Pb and B) is very effective for geographical discrimination is that it is highly precise (Cellier et al., 2021). However, the downside of achieving this level of precision is that this approach is time-consuming, costly to implement and requires very expensive equipment. Precision, in other words measurement uncertainty, is essential for evaluating and comparing quantitative results. Indeed, low measurement uncertainty allows for reliable data comparison and therefore relevant information. The reduction of the measurement uncertainty should therefore be a goal. Levels of precision for the isotopic measurements of Sr, Pb and B are far below the percent, even the per-thousand (Cellier et al., 2021). In comparison, depending on

concentration levels, the precision obtained by external calibration when using ICP-MS is usually between 5 and 10% (Vacchina et al., 2023). The precision associated to ID is expected much less (Rodriguez-Gonzalez & Garcia Alonso, 2019).

Indeed, ID is based on the addition of a known quantity of an enriched isotope (the spike) to the samples to be analyzed at the very beginning of the analytical process on a weight basis. The determination of the concentration after calculation integrating the isotopic ratio of the elements is performed at the end of the whole procedure and integrates anything arising during the sample preparation. The main advantage of ID over other quantification procedures is that losses of substance, after the sample has been equilibrated with the tracer, are compensated. So, no recovery corrections for non-quantitative sample preparation procedures need to be performed. Additionally, the control of final volumes after dilution procedures is not required. Another important advantage of ID is that matrix effects are offset since any factor increasing or decreasing the sensitivity of the analyte will affect in the same way the spike employed. Finally, the measurement of isotope compositions is normally free from signal drift. Thus, overall, ID procedures are more accurate and precise than any other analytical procedure (Rodriguez-Gonzalez & Garcia Alonso, 2019).

Furthermore, to obtain the best possible results, the absolute amounts of analyte and spike in the final solution must be approximately equal (Rodriguez-Gonzalez & Garcia Alonso, 2019). Considering the analytical process applied, a wine sample uptake of 1 mL and a volume of the spike added of 100 μ L, the spike was built to contain a concentration of each element approximately 10 times higher than the one expected in the wine samples. This expected concentration was evaluated at first from a global overview of the average concentrations reported in the literature. The exact composition of the spike is given in the 2.3. section.

Table 1
: Figures of merit of the method.

Element	Natural concentration	Recoveries	Precision intra-day	Precision inter-day	LOQ (μ g/L)
Li	9.5 \pm 0.7 μ g/L	101 \pm 7%	2.3–3.6%	6.5%	2
B	6277 \pm 63 μ g/L	110 \pm 3%	1.9–3.7%	2.4%	10
Cr	10 \pm 1 μ g/L	98 \pm 11%	4.4–5.6%	10.7%	5
Fe	1730 \pm 71 μ g/L	99 \pm 5%	1.9–4.2%	4.9%	10
Ni	17 \pm 1 μ g/L	101 \pm 5%	1.2–6.5%	4.6%	2
Cu	159 \pm 2 μ g/L	105 \pm 2%	1.1–1.8%	2.1%	5
Zn	696 \pm 5 μ g/L	93 \pm 3%	0.8–2.4%	3.7%	5
Rb	1545 \pm 85 μ g/L	98 \pm 5%	0.9–2.4%	5.6%	2
Sr	438 \pm 3	111 \pm 1%	0.8–5.7%	1.1%	2
Mo	5.7 \pm 0.3 μ g/L	92 \pm 5%	1.5–3.7%	5.3%	2
Cd	0.199 \pm 0.008 μ g/L	96 \pm 9%	3.3–4.5%	9.8%	0.05
Ba	207 \pm 3 μ g/L	99 \pm 3%	1.3–4.0%	2.9%	1
Pb	9.7 \pm 0.2 μ g/L	103 \pm 7%	1.7–2.0%	6.8%	0.5
As	1.6 \pm 0.1 μ g/L	91 \pm 5%	2.8–4.7%	5.6%	0.05
Al	232 \pm 35 μ g/L	98 \pm 11%	2.5–9.9%	11.0%	50
Co	2.7 \pm 0.2 μ g/L	94 \pm 5%	3.0–5.0%	5.1%	0.02
Mn	1210 \pm 108 μ g/L	101 \pm 8%	2.9–6.5%	7.5%	5
V	0.60 \pm 0.02 μ g/L	93 \pm 8%	2.9–3.2%	8.8%	0.5
Na	10.5 \pm 0.8 mg/L	105 \pm 5%	0.7–1.8%	4.5%	200
K	1141 \pm 41 mg/L	100 \pm 5%	1.6–4.1%	5.3%	200
S	203 \pm 5 mg/L	102 \pm 7%	1.4–3.8%	6.7%	500
Ca	44 \pm 2 mg/L	98 \pm 9%	2.2–3.8%	8.8%	200
Mg	144 \pm 5 mg/L	102 \pm 3%	1.4–2.4%	3.3%	20

3.2. Analytical figures of merit of the method

The analytical figures of merit of the method are presented Table 1. In the absence of a Certified Reference Material (CRM) for multi-elemental determination in wine, they were evaluated from a sample made from an equal mixture of very different wines (see section 2.1.) spiked in order to nearly quadruple the natural concentration of the element investigated. The spiked wine sample was analyzed ($n = 6$) on 3 different days.

Intra-day precisions were on average in the range 2–3% for the elements measured by ID, slightly higher for the elements with a concentration close to the quantification limit (Cd, Cr and Mo). Inter-day precision is, as expected, higher but it is important to point out that, on average, inter-day precision of the elements measured by ID (5.1%) is lower than that of the elements measured by external calibration (6.7%). This trend illustrates an important advantage of MID, in this case that the impact of the change of the day analysis (which could also be extended to changes in operator) on the result is minimized. This is of primary importance when an extensive database is to be constructed. Recoveries ranged between 91 and 111%, again regardless of the concentration level and the quantification method used. LOQ was calculated according to the IUPAC criteria as the concentration corresponding to 10 times the standard deviation of the blank ($n = 6$). As expected, they differ strongly depending on the element. For trace elements, LOQs were usually at the $\mu\text{g/L}$ level, which allows the detection of trace elements important for geographical assessment, such as Li, for example. For major elements, they were much higher, but it has to be pointed out that the sensitivity of the instrument was artificially decreased for these elements. They remain anyway much lower than the concentrations expected in the wine samples.

3.3. Contribution of MID to the improvement of the precision of the measurement

In order to compare the effectiveness of MID with external calibration, the 13 elements that could be analyzed by ID were analyzed using both ID and external calibration. In each case, 6 individual analyses were performed per sample and the average and the standard deviation of the 6 corresponding results were calculated. Fig. 2 displays the average RSD obtained for each element obtained by MID compared to external calibration.

In this figure, the elements were classified in ascending order of

deviation from quantification limit (represented by the grey line connected to the right axis). The RSD was improved of at least 30% (Li) and up to a factor 4 (Mo). For most of the elements, the use of ID allowed a decrease of the RSD of about a factor 2. Thanks to ID, RSD on the results could be brought below 5% and could be in the range of 1–3%. The only elements presenting a RSD higher than 5% were Cr, Mo and Cd which have concentrations at or very close to the quantification level. However, even for them, a significant improvement in RSD was observed compared to quantification by external calibration. Regardless of the concentration ranges, an average recovery of $100 \pm 13\%$ was obtained between the two quantification methods. It seems therefore that, at least for the wine matrix, the contribution of ID to the discrimination of the samples is expected to be more related to the improvement of the measurement uncertainty than to the improvement of the accuracy, as already mentioned in the previous section. These results clearly demonstrate the general improvement in routine measurement of multielement determination in terms of RSDs.

3.4. Contribution of MID to the improvement of the discrimination

The goal of improving the precision of the measurement comes from the fact that this should lead to improved discrimination. To verify this, the 13 elements that can be measured both by ID and by external calibration were measured in both ways in the set of 25 samples from three different countries and selected to evaluate the improvements brought by using ID compared to external calibration. The mono-isotopic elements and the major elements were not considered here as they can only be measured by external calibration.

The measured concentrations were then subjected to statistical analysis using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA). Both are common dimensionality reduction techniques but LDA is supervised contrary to PCA. Since it is not possible to take measurement uncertainty into account with either PCA or LDA, instead of considering the average concentration measured for each sample analyzed, the extreme values were taken into account. For example, if the result obtained for a given sample was $20 \pm 1 \mu\text{g/L}$, both 19 and 21 $\mu\text{g/L}$ values were considered to perform the statistics. In this way, it was possible to take into account the spread of the results. The statistical representations are presented in Fig. 3.

The first obvious result is that a supervised statistical treatment is necessary to achieve a good discrimination of the three geographical origins. If trends tend to appear using PCA (Fig. 3a and b), PC1 + PC2

Fig. 2. Average RSD ($n = 25$) on 6 individual results per sample depending on the analytical approach. Histograms are connected to the left axis: orange are obtained by ID and blue by external calibration. The grey curve is connected to the right axis. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Contribution of ID to the discrimination of the wine origin. (a) PCA representation from results obtained by external calibration. (b) PCA representation from results obtained by MID. (c) LDA representation from results obtained by external calibration. (d) LDA representation from results obtained by MID. ● Italy. ● Spain. ● Tunisia. +: center of gravity. O: 95% confidence level.

never exceeds 55%, whereas it is commonly accepted that a minimum of 70% is necessary to prove a good separation. On the other hand, a good separation of the three groups could be achieved using LDA (Fig. 3c and d). This visual observation is confirmed by the values of R^2 (> 0.9) and of the λ of Wilk (< 0.05).

Focusing now on the LDA representation and comparing the results obtained by ID (Fig. 3d) and external calibration (Fig. 3c), it appears that the statistical parameters used to evaluate the goodness of the discrimination are better for ID than for external calibration. Indeed, R^2 is closer to 1 (from 0.99843 to 0.99967) and λ of Wilk is lower (from 0.0247832 to 0.0212499). Even though in this example a good discrimination could already be achieved using quantification by external calibration, due to the intrinsic discriminating power of the elements selected, a better discrimination potential can be obtained when using the MID method instead of external calibration strategies. The lower dispersion of the results obtained by ID later translates into improved geographical discrimination.

To conclude on the use of MID rather than external calibration, anytime possible, two main advantages can be highlighted, apart this measurement precision improvement. The first one is that this method can be considered to be the closest to IS system which is of primary importance when forecasting the development of a large database. Second, compared to traditional calibration methods, once the concentrations of the isotopic standards are established and despite their cost

that may be significant, just a small amount is added at the very beginning of the sample preparation protocol. Then a very significant time saving is achieved for all dilution and analysis tasks. However, it cannot be ignored that some elements cannot be measured by MID. As already previously discussed, one of the advantages of the MID is that it corrects perfectly the matrix effects which might not be the case with external calibration. For the 13 elements that can be measured in both ways, the concentration obtained by external calibration was compared to the one obtained by MID, considered as the reference. An average recovery of 104% was obtained between both results. Moreover, a wine sample coming from a proficiency testing program (BIPEA, France) was also analyzed. For the few elements (Mn, Na, Ca, Mg and K) for which an indicative value existed and that our protocol measures by external calibration, an average recovery of 103% was obtained between the indicative value and our result. Therefore, even if the precision of the measurement by external calibration is not as good as for the MID approach, the overall accuracy of these measurements is not significantly impacted.

Also, this method could be fully automated to allow very high sample throughput with excellent precision and accuracy overall. At this stage, the analysis step by ICP-MS is already automated. The most time-consuming step remains the sample preparation one. Since the wine samples and the isotopic spike solution are in liquid form, systems to automate the sample preparation phase (mineralization and dilution)

are commercially available and can be implemented.

3.5. Inter-bottle reproducibility

As the protocol developed is assumed to be applied on bottled wine, it was important to check the inter-bottle reproducibility. For 21 samples covering three different geographical origins, two different bottles of the same wine were analyzed and the results compared. Fig. 4 presents bottle-to-bottle reproducibility data for two elements chosen to make the demonstration: lithium and strontium. The choice was deliberate on two grounds. First, both elements are among the most geographically informative tracers in the dataset, lithium is sensitive to soil mineralogy and hydrology and strontium to bedrock geology, making their reproducibility directly relevant to the discrimination results that follow. Second, they span a wide concentration range: lithium concentrations across the sample set range from 5 to 50 $\mu\text{g/L}$, while strontium ranges from 100 to 1100 $\mu\text{g/L}$. An average recovery of $102 \pm 4\%$ was obtained. This shows the homogeneity of the wine, regardless the bottle sampled. This is of primary importance for the further applications of the database.

3.6. Application of the method developed to the high resolution discrimination at the level of the “Coteaux” of Jurançon

In order to evaluate the full potential of this method in terms of very high geographical resolution, it was applied to a very small wine-growing area, the Côteaux de Jurançon, located in the foothills of the Pyrenees in the southwestern France. The “Jurançon” appellation vineyard covers an area of nearly 1000 ha, planted on clay and sandstone soils in the south. In the north, the soil substrates are different, consisting of solidified detrital rocks covered with pebbles and gravel eroded from the Pyrenees Mountain and deposited by the Gave de Pau river. In these “terroirs”, the wine is cultivated and produced in three different hills, made of different soil systems, representing a small area of about 10 km^2 . A well identified selection of DOC wine samples was obtained directly from the wine producers in order to have the best and most representative coverage of the production in these areas. A number of 50 samples covering almost equally the three different “Coteaux” was analyzed: Jurançon ($n = 15$), Lasseube ($n = 16$) and Monein ($n = 19$).

3.6.1. Multivariate statistical analysis

Six different statistical treatments were applied to this set of 50 samples divided in 3 different classes: (1) Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) that is a supervised method that finds linear combinations of features to maximize separation between predefined classes; (2)

Fig. 4. In between bottle variability displayed on two elements (Li and Sr) having a large difference of concentration amplitude and that are important for discrimination of origin: Li and Sr. Two consecutive bars of the same color represent two different bottles of the same wine.

Quadratic Linear Analysis (QDA) that allows each class to have its own covariance matrix, enabling quadratic decision boundaries for improved flexibility with non-spherical data; (3) k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) that assigns a label to a data point based on the majority class of its k closest neighbors; (4) Random Forest (RF) that builds multiple decision trees and merges their predictions; (5) Support Vector Machine (SVM) that identifies the optimal hyperplane to separate classes by maximizing the margin; and (6) Naïve Bayes (NB) that is a probabilistic classifier based on Bayes' theorem, assuming feature independence given the class label.

The confusion matrices obtained for each treatment are presented [Table 2](#) and the 2D projection of the data is shown [Fig. 5](#).

These confusion matrices clearly show the importance of the statistical treatment applied. No area is always or never correctly classified, whatever the statistical treatment applied. Whereas RF allows reaching an overall correct classification of 100%, kNN and NB correct classification rates do not exceed 80%. In between, LDA allows a 100% correct geographical assignment for the Lasseube and Monein areas but misclassified one sample from Jurançon in Lasseube. This can be corrected if QDA is used instead of LDA. SVM was also quite efficient with two areas (Jurançon and Lasseube) 100% correctly classified. Therefore, the integration of different classification methods gives the possibility to find the best classifier for each group. At this level, QDA and Random Forest turns out to be the most suitable.

3.6.2. Comparison with literature data

No study focusing on the discrimination of “Jurançon” wines has ever been published. It was therefore not possible to compare our results with literature data. It was therefore decided to compare our results with results obtained in geographical areas of almost the same size. In the French Bordeaux wines region, [Epova et al. \(2019\)](#) managed to

Table 2

Confusion matrices obtained for the six statistical treatments investigated.

LDA			
	Jurançon	Lasseube	Monein
Jurançon	93.3%	6.7%	0%
Lasseube	0%	100%	0%
Monein	0%	0%	100%
QDA			
	Jurançon	Lasseube	Monein
Jurançon	100%	0%	0%
Lasseube	0%	100%	0%
Monein	0%	0%	100%
kNN			
	Jurançon	Lasseube	Monein
Jurançon	66.7%	0%	33.3%
Lasseube	25.0%	75.0%	0%
Monein	0%	25.0%	75.0%
RF			
	Jurançon	Lasseube	Monein
Jurançon	100%	0%	0%
Lasseube	0%	100%	0%
Monein	0%	0%	100%
SVM			
	Jurançon	Lasseube	Monein
Jurançon	100%	0%	0%
Lasseube	0%	100%	0%
Monein	0%	25.0%	75.0%
NB			
	Jurançon	Lasseube	Monein
Jurançon	83.3%	0%	16.7%
Lasseube	0%	100%	0%
Monein	0%	40.0%	60.0%

discriminate Pomerol and Saint-Emilion appellations using $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotopic ratio. No overlap was observed but only 11 Pomerol and 4 Saint-Emilion wines were investigated. More recently, [Su et al. \(2024\)](#) used a mixture of 45 elements plus $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ to discriminate wines from three towns in the Deqin County (China). If the oxygen and carbon isotopic ratios did not show any discriminant ability, the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model draw an accuracy of 95.2% with the elemental profile.

In addition, [Rapa et al. \(2023\)](#) conducted a study very similar to ours. They measured 63 elements and 6 isotopes (B, Sr and Pb) in 219 wines from the Veneto region (Italy) shared into 7 PDOs. Even though the geographical area was much larger than that studied here, the multivariate statistical treatment applied was very similar to ours. As here, they observed that the classification methods were not equally effective with each other and between the PDOs. Whereas, in average, kNN was by far the least efficient method, the others were not that different, SVM being the most efficient one, followed by RF. The same kind of trend was observed in our study. Nonetheless, the best correct classification percentage for a pair classification method/PDO was only of 84.8% whereas in this study 100% was regularly achieved. It has anyway to point out that more groups had to be discriminated in the study of [Rapa et al. \(2023\)](#).

To conclude, to our knowledge, the study presented here seems to be the best geographical localization and assessment of origin to date on a such small geographic area. It illustrates the power of the analytical method developed. Moreover, the elements analyzed are more targeted, only 23, simultaneously analyzable, which make the method much more cost and time effective than an approach by MC-ICP-MS would be, with an efficiency of the same order of magnitude, or even better.

3.6.3. Factors impacting the discrimination

In this set of 50 samples, the geographical separation of the three hills was not the only one investigated. Organic and conventional wines on one side, 2021 and 2022 vintages on the other side and, apart two samples stored in a stoneware container, samples previously stored in wooden containers or tanks were on a third side were almost equally distributed in the three geographical groups. Attempts to discriminate organic versus conventional wines or wines previously stored in wooden containers or tanks using the elemental profile all failed. This tends to show that the impact of the winemaking process on the elemental profile is negligible in comparison to the soil the vine has grown on. Attempts to discriminate the two vintages also failed. But it has to be pointed out that the two vintages investigated were consecutive. [Donard et al. \(2024\)](#) have shown significant and regular variations of the concentration of certain elements, such as Ca, K or Fe, in a vertical of Champaign starting in the 80's and attributed to the global warming. This means that, on a medium-term basis, the database should be updated to maintain its full potential.

4. Conclusion

The continuous development of ICP-MS enabling multi-elemental analysis is now increasingly used to address the origin of products, particularly wine. We present in this paper a novel approach that will significantly enhance these developments, promoting very high potential for high geographical resolution. Indeed, we have developed a novel calibration method using labeled isotopes (hence using the multi-isotopic potential of detection of ICP-MS) to promote a simultaneous multi-isotopic quantitation of 13 elements such as Li, B, Cr, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, Rb, Sr, Mo, Cd, Ba and Pb. In addition, the quantitative approach was simultaneously extended by complementing the calibration strategies using MID with external calibration for another 10 elements Na, Mg, Al, S, K, Ca, V, Mn, Co, and As. This combined approach was implemented since many of these elements are mono-isotopic. The method was first validated using a model wine consisting of a mixture of wines from different origins. The method has demonstrated very promising

Fig. 5. QDA 2D projection of wines from the three different hills of the Jurançon appellation, with +: center of gravity and O: 95% confidence level. In inset, the position of the hills on the map.

performance in terms of robustness and broad applicability, with excellent performance in detection criteria. Compared to traditional calibration procedures, MID is much closer and easier to trace back to the IS system. A specific comparative assessment of MID methods versus external calibration was carried out on a set of wine samples from different countries around the Mediterranean Sea. Using statistical calculations, it was demonstrated that both methods (external calibration and MID) would allow the origin of the wines studied to be discriminated. However, the MID method had slightly better overall results in terms of discrimination.

This MID method, combined with complementary calibration procedures, was applied to the general discrimination of French wine samples produced in different regions. The results were excellent, with high to very high classification rates, most determinations exceeding 90% and reaching as high as 100%. The MID method was then applied to a very small wine-producing area located on the various hills of the Coteaux de Jurançon, and the results were also excellent with 100% correct classification when using Random Forest or Quadratic Discrimination Analysis. These are the best results achieved to date in terms of geographical discrimination. Furthermore, due to the very high precision of this method, it could be applied on a yearly routine basis, which would eventually make it possible to establish a link between these results and climate change. Finally, it is still possible to significantly enhance the performance of the method by automating it, enlarging the number of elements simultaneously deterred, and by improving statistical analysis using AI (Artificial Intelligence) adapted to wine.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Véronique Vacchina: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Ylenia Pieracci:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Mauro Di Stasi:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Nicola Mercanti:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Camila Cazorla Ares:** Writing – review &

editing, Formal analysis. **Pablo Rodriguez:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Christophe Lahüt:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Fabienne Séby:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Olivier F.X. Donard:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2026.149221>.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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